

Concurrent Intestinal Malrotation and Meckel's Diverticulum Presenting as Small Bowel Obstruction in an Adult: A Case Report

Authors:

Dr. Shefali sarfaraz khan¹, Dr. Gopinath Vemulamada²

¹Resident, Dept. of General Surgery, MGM medical college & hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar.

²Resident, Dept. of General Surgery, MGM medical college & hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Shefali sarfaraz khan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18947905>

Received: 08-February-2026, Revised: 23-February-2026, Accepted: 10-March-2026, Online First: 11-March-2026

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Intestinal malrotation is a rare congenital anomaly resulting from abnormal rotation of the midgut around the superior mesenteric artery, while Meckel's diverticulum represents persistence of the vitellointestinal duct. The coexistence of these two anomalies in adults is extremely uncommon and may present as acute or recurrent intestinal obstruction.

Case Presentation: We report a 19-year-old female with a long history of intermittent abdominal pain, decreased appetite, and constipation. CT imaging revealed acute small bowel obstruction with mid-ileal stricture and intestinal malrotation. Diagnostic laparoscopy demonstrated a tubular structure connecting the small bowel to the umbilicus, suspicious for Meckel's diverticulum, with constrictive bands and adhesions causing obstruction. The patient underwent supraumbilical laparotomy, adhesiolysis, ileo-ileal resection, and end-to-end anastomosis. Postoperative recovery was uneventful.

Discussion: The concurrence of intestinal malrotation and Meckel's diverticulum is rare, with few cases reported in literature. Both anomalies predispose to recurrent abdominal pain and obstruction, complicating diagnosis in adults. Early recognition and surgical intervention are essential to prevent complications such as gangrene, perforation, or short bowel syndrome.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of considering unusual congenital associations in patients with recurrent abdominal pain or unexplained obstructive symptoms. Diagnostic laparoscopy and timely surgical management remain crucial in achieving favorable outcomes.

Keywords: *Intestinal malrotation, Meckel's diverticulum*

INTRODUCTION:

Intestinal malrotation is a congenital anomaly resulting from incomplete or abnormal rotation of the midgut around the superior mesenteric artery (SMA) during embryogenesis. It can present variably, ranging from asymptomatic cases to acute intestinal obstruction in children or adults.^{1,2}

Meckel's diverticulum, another congenital abnormality, arises from the persistence of the vitellointestinal duct and is considered the most common anomaly of the gastrointestinal tract, with an incidence of approximately 2%.³ It is a true diverticulum located on the antimesenteric border of the distal ileum and may contain heterotopic

gastric or pancreatic mucosa. Symptomatic cases often present with bleeding, obstruction, or inflammation.⁴

The concurrence of intestinal malrotation and Meckel's diverticulum is rare, particularly in adults, and may complicate the clinical picture by causing recurrent or acute intestinal obstruction.^{5,6} Reporting such cases is important to highlight diagnostic challenges and surgical management strategies. Here, we present a case of a 19-year-old female with intestinal malrotation and suspected Meckel's diverticulum presenting as small bowel obstruction.

CASE REPORT:

A 19-year-old female presented to the outpatient department of MGM Hospital with a long-standing history of intermittent abdominal pain for 2–3 years, associated with decreased appetite and constipation occurring on and off for the past 3 years. Her nutritional status was poor, with a height of 145 cm, weight of 30 kg, and a body mass index (BMI) of 14, indicating significant undernutrition.

On systemic examination, the abdomen was soft, non-tender, non-distended, and bowel sounds were present. Despite the absence of acute peritoneal signs, her chronic complaints warranted further evaluation. A contrast-enhanced CT scan of the abdomen and pelvis revealed features suggestive of acute small bowel obstruction with a mid-ileal stricture and evidence of intestinal malrotation.

The patient was posted for diagnostic laparoscopy with the possibility of exploratory laparotomy depending on

intraoperative findings. During laparoscopy, a left-sided appendectomy was performed. In addition, a tubular structure was noted connecting the small bowel to the umbilicus, raising suspicion of Meckel's diverticulum. Dense constrictive bands and adhesions were seen in association with this structure, contributing to small bowel obstruction.

Given these findings, a supraumbilical incision was taken, adhesiolysis was performed, and the obstructed bowel loops were exteriorized. An ileo-ileal resection with end-to-end anastomosis was carried out to relieve the obstruction and remove the diseased segment. The postoperative course was uneventful, with the patient recovering well. She was discharged with advice regarding nutritional rehabilitation, stoma care precautions, and regular follow-up to monitor for late complications such as stricture formation or recurrent obstruction.

Fig 1: A. laparoscopic view of left sided appendix B. Meckel's diverticulum with adhesions

DISCUSSION:

Intestinal malrotation represents the partial or complete failure of rotation of the midgut around the axis of the SMA in a counter-clockwise direction during embryogenesis.^{1,2} Malrotation beyond the neonatal period is uncommon, but when present in adolescents or adults, it often manifests as chronic intermittent abdominal pain, subacute obstruction, or acute intestinal obstruction.

Meckel's diverticulum is the most common congenital anomaly of the gastrointestinal tract, arising from incomplete regression of the vitellointestinal duct.³ Although its incidence is approximately 2%, most cases remain asymptomatic. Symptomatic presentations include bleeding, obstruction, diverticulitis, or perforation.⁴

The concurrence of intestinal malrotation and Meckel's diverticulum is rare, with only a handful of cases reported in literature.^{5,6} In most previously described cases, patients presented with recurrent abdominal pain since childhood, progressing to acute obstruction in adolescence or adulthood. In our patient, the presence of a tubular structure connecting the small bowel to the umbilicus, suspicious for Meckel's diverticulum, along with constrictive bands and adhesions, contributed to small bowel obstruction.

Surgical management remains the cornerstone of treatment. In our case, diagnostic laparoscopy revealed the abnormal structure and adhesions, necessitating conversion to open surgery. Adhesiolysis, ileo-ileal resection, and end-to-end anastomosis were performed successfully. The postoperative course was uneventful,

underscoring the importance of timely surgical intervention. Literature emphasizes that diagnostic laparoscopy can aid in early identification of such rare congenital anomalies, preventing progression to gangrene or perforation.

This case reinforces the need to consider unusual congenital associations in patients with recurrent abdominal pain or unexplained obstructive symptoms. The combination of malrotation and Meckel's diverticulum may predispose to recurrent subacute obstruction before culminating in an acute event, as seen here. Early recognition and appropriate surgical management are critical to improving outcomes and preventing long-term complications.

CONCLUSION:

The coexistence of intestinal malrotation and Meckel's diverticulum is an uncommon clinical entity, particularly in adolescents and adults. Although each anomaly may remain silent for years, their concurrence can predispose patients to recurrent or acute intestinal obstruction, as demonstrated in our case. Early recognition of atypical presentations such as chronic abdominal pain, unexplained nutritional compromise, or recurrent obstructive symptoms is essential.

Diagnostic laparoscopy plays a pivotal role in identifying rare congenital abnormalities and guiding timely surgical intervention. Definitive management through adhesiolysis, resection, and anastomosis ensures resolution of obstruction and prevents long-term complications. This case underscores the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for unusual congenital associations in patients with recurrent abdominal complaints, and highlights the value of prompt surgical management in achieving favorable outcomes.

REFERENCES:

1. Buchmiller TL, Raghavendran K, Chen W. Intestinal malrotation in adults. UpToDate. Updated Oct 23, 2025.
2. Rodrigues JQ, Sousa AC, Pinto JP, Costa JM, Manso F, Ribeiro AC, Pereira JC. Adult-onset congenital intestinal malrotation presenting with volvulus: a case report and review of the literature. *Surg Gastroenterol Oncol.* 2025;30(3):823. doi:10.21614/sgo-823.
3. Yadav A, Salim M, Sharma S. Exploring the various presentations of Meckel's diverticulum in adults. *J Contemp Clin Pract.* 2025;11(4):318-23.
4. Ho KA, Srinivasan R. Torsion of Meckel's diverticulum: a case report and literature review. *J Surg Case Rep.*

2024;2024(1):rjad740.
doi:10.1093/jscr/rjad740.

5. Harvey JS, Giles GR. Associated midgut malrotation and Meckel's diverticulum presenting in adult life. *Br J Surg.* 1974;61(2):157-8.
6. Taylor H, Venza M, Badvie S. Concurrent perforated Meckel's diverticulum and intestinal malrotation in an 8-year-old boy. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2015;2015:bcr2015212377.